

Characterization of a wiener process taking values in a Hilbert space

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Abstract

This paper characterize wiener process by taking values in a Hilbert space.

A standard wiener process is stochastic process $\{W_t\}_{t \geq 0+}$ indexed by nonnegative real numbers t with the following properties:

$$W_0=0$$

With probability 1, the function $t \rightarrow W_t$ is continuous in t .

The process $\{W_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ has stationary, independent increments.

The increments $W_{t+s} - W_s$ has the NORMAL $(0,t)$ distribution

Keywords: Wiener process; Hilbert space; Characteristic function; Orthonormal system.

1 Introduction

Characterization theorems for wieners process by taking values in a Hilbert space have been discussed.

Renyi [1] discussed the characterization of a Wiener process taking values in a Hilbert space a follows:

Let Δ be the interval $[0,1]$ and B denote the σ - algebra of Borel subsets of $[0,1]$.

For each $\Delta \in B$, let $\Phi(\Delta)$ be a random element taking values in a real separable Hilbert space H . Suppose (Δ) satisfies the following properties.

(i) If (Φ) and (Δ') are disjoint Borel subsets of $[0,1]$, then $\Phi(\Delta)$ and $\Phi(\Delta')$ are independent.

$$\Phi(\Delta \cup \Delta') = \Phi(\Delta) + \Phi(\Delta')$$

(ii) $\Phi(\Delta)$ has stationary increments (ie) $\Phi(\Delta)$ and $\Phi(\Delta')$ are identically distributed if Φ and Δ' have the same Lebesgue measure.

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- (iii) If μ_1 denotes the probability measure of $\Phi [0,t]$ then μ_1 converges weakly to the distribution degenerate at the origin as $t \rightarrow 0$.

For any two \bar{x}, \bar{y} in R^k

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \bar{x}, \bar{y} \rangle &= \sum_{j=1}^k x_j y_j \\
 \mu(\bar{t}) &= \int e^{i(\bar{t}, \bar{x})} \cdot d\mu(\bar{x}), \quad \bar{t} \in R^k
 \end{aligned}$$

The complex valued function μ^\wedge on R^k is called the Fourier transform or characteristic function of the probability measure. If \bar{f} is an R^k valued random variable on a probability space (Ω, s, p) and $\mu = p\bar{f}^{-1}$ is the distribution of \bar{f} , its characteristic function μ^\wedge is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu^\wedge(\bar{t}) &= \int e^{i(\bar{t}, \bar{x})} \cdot d\mu(\bar{x}) \\
 &= \int e^{i(\bar{t}, \bar{f})} \cdot dp \\
 &= E[e^{i(\bar{t}, \bar{f})}]
 \end{aligned}$$

μ^\wedge is the characteristics function of the random variable \bar{f}

2 Proposition 1

The multivariate normal distribution in R^k with mean vector \bar{m} and co - variance matrix Σ has characteristic function $e^{i(\bar{t}, \bar{m}) - 1/2 \bar{t}^{-1} \Sigma \bar{t}}$.

2.1 Definition 1

2.1.1 Orthonormal System

A sequence $\xi_n (n = 1, 2, \dots \dots \dots)$ of random variable on a probability space

$S = (\Omega, A, P)$ is called on orthonormal system, if ξ_n belongs to the Hilbert space

$L_2(S)$.

(ie),

(ξ_n^2) exists and has

$$n$$

$$(\xi_n^2) = 1, n = 1, 2, \dots \dots \dots$$

$$[\xi_n \xi_m] = 0, n \neq m$$

2.2 Definition 2

2.2.1 Hilbert Space

A Banach space is called a Hilbert space, if the function (x, y) inner product of x and y has the following properties.

1. $(x, y) = (y, x)$
2. $(x, x) = \|x\|^2$
3. For fixed y , $(x) = (x, y)$ is a linear functional. (i.e) $[A(ax + by)] = aA(x) + b(A(y))$

2.3 Definition 3

Complete Orthonormal System

The orthonormal system $\{\xi_n\}$ is complete if $\eta \in L_2(S), E(\eta\xi_n) = 0, n = 1, 2, \dots$ it follows that $\eta = 0$ almost surely.

2.4 Definition 4

2.4.1 Fourier Co-efficient

If $\{\xi_n\}$ is an orthonormal system on S and η is an arbitrary random variable $\eta \in L_2(S)$, the sequence $C_n = E[\eta\xi_n]$ is called the sequence of fourier co-efficient of η and the series $\sum C_n \xi_n$ is fourier series of η with respect to $\{\xi_n\}$.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n^2 = E(\eta^2)$$

is Parseval's relation.

2.5 Definition 5

2.5.1 Rademacher Function

Let S be Lebesgue probability space and consider the Rademacher function.

$$R_n(x) = (\sin 2^n \pi x) \quad (0 \leq x \leq 1, n = 1, 2, \dots)$$

2.6 Definition 6

2.6.1 Walsh Functions

Let us now define the functions $W_n(x), 0 \leq x \leq 1, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ as follows.

Let $W_0(x), 0 \leq x \leq 1$.

Further if the representation of $n \geq 1$ in the binary system is $n = 2^{k_1} + 2^{k_2} + \dots + 2^{k_r}$ are integer

$$\text{Put } W_n(x) = R_{k_1+1}(x) R_{k_2+1}(x) \dots R_{k_r+1}(x).$$

The function $W_n(x)$, $[n = 0, 1, 2, \dots]$ are called Walsh functions.

To prove that $\{w_n(x)\}$ form an orthonormal system on the Lebesgue probability space. If $\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n$ are independent random variables with finite expectation then $\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n$ also has finite expectation and

$$E(\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n) = \prod_{k=1}^n E(\xi_k).$$

bability space.

3 Theorem 1

If the random variables ξ_n are independent ($n = 1, 2, \dots$), $E(\xi_n^2) = 1$ and $E(\xi_n) = 0$ for $n = 1, 2, \dots$ then all the products $\xi_{k_1}, \xi_{k_2}, \dots, \xi_{k_r}$ ($1 \leq k_1 < k_2 < \dots < k_r, r = 1, 2, \dots$) belong to $L^2(s)$ and they form together with the constant 1 and orthonormal system.

Proof

$$\text{We have } E(\xi_{k_1}, \xi_{k_2}, \dots, \xi_{k_r}) = \prod_{j=1}^r E(\xi_{k_j}) = 1$$

If we take any two non identical product $\xi_{k_1}, \xi_{k_2}, \dots, \xi_{k_r}$.

$$(k_1 < k_2 < \dots < k_r) \text{ and } (l_1 < l_2 < \dots < l_s) \text{ and } (l_1 < l_2 < \dots < l_s).$$

$$E(\xi_n) = 0, n \geq 1 \text{ and their product has expectation zero.}$$

Then we have $E(l^2) = 1$.

$$E(1 \cdot \xi_{k_1}, \xi_{k_2}, \dots, \xi_{k_r}) = 0$$

Next to prove that this system is complete.

Let x be a real number $0 \leq x < 1$ which is not a binary rational number.

Let the binary expansion of x be $x = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\xi_k(x)}{2^k}$ ($\xi_k(x) = 0$ or 1)

$$\text{Then } \tilde{\xi}_k(x) = \frac{1 - R_k(x)}{2}$$

$\tilde{\xi}_k(x) = 1$ or -1 when $\xi_k(x) = 0$ or 1 .

Let $i(x)$ denotes the indicator function of the interval $(\frac{m}{2^n}, \frac{m+1}{2^n})$ where m and n are non negative integers and $0 \leq m < 2^n$.

Let the binary expansion of $m / 2^n$ be

$$\frac{m}{2^n} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\delta_k}{2^k} \quad (\delta_k = 0 \text{ or } 1, k = 1, 2, \dots, n)$$

Then $i_n(x)$ can be written in the form

$$i_{n,m}(x) = \sum_{l=0}^{2^n-1} a_{n,m,l} W_l(x)$$

It follows that if $f(x) \in L_2(S)$ is such a function that

$$\int f(x) w_n(x) dx = 0, n = 0, 1, \dots$$

Then we have

$$\int_{m/2^n}^{(m+1)/2^n} f(x) dx = 0, 0 \leq m < 2^n, n = 1, 2, \dots$$

$$\int_{m/2^n}^{(m+1)/2^n} f(x) dx = 0, 0 \leq m < 2^n, n = 1, 2, \dots$$

$$\int_{m/2^n}^{(m+1)/2^n} f(x) dx = 0, 0 \leq m < 2^n, n = 1, 2, \dots$$

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$$\int_{m/2^n}^{(m+1)/2^n} f(x) dx = 0, 0 \leq m < 2^n, n = 1, 2, \dots$$

$$0$$

t

$$\text{Thus putting } (x) = \int_0^t (t) = 0.$$

0

We get $(r) = 0$ for every binary rational number r in $(0,1)$. The function (x) being the indefinite integral of an integrable function is continuous thus $(x) = 0$ for all X in $[0,1]$.

Therefore $(x) = 0$ for almost all x .

Therefore the system of Walsh functions is complete.

The series defining (t) is almost surely convergent, because denoting by $e_t(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & 0 < x < 1 \\ 0 & 0 < t < 1 \end{cases}$ the indicator of the interval $(0,t)$ and taking into account that

$$\int_0^t W_n(x) dx = \int_0^t e_t(x) w_n(x) dx$$

$$0 \qquad 0$$

and Fourier Walsh co-efficient of function $e_t(x)$. Since $\{e_n(x)\}$ is a complete orthonormal system. We get from Parseval's relation,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \int_0^t W_n(x) dx = t$$

Therefore $\int_0^t \int_0^s W_n(x) dx = t \int_0^s W_n(x) dx = 1$

The Parseval's relation $\Rightarrow 0 < s < t < 1$

$$[\eta(s)\eta(t)] = E \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \int_0^s W_n(x) dx \int_0^t W_n(x) dx$$

$$= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \int_0^s W_n(x) dx \int_0^t W_n(x) dx = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \int_0^s W_n(x) dx$$

$$= \int_0^s e_s(x)e_t(x) dx = s$$

$$[(t_1) - (s_1)][(t_2) - (s_2)] = t_1 - s_1 - t_1 + s_1 = 0$$

$$[(t) - (s)]^2 = t + s - 2s = t - s \text{ if } s < t$$

Similarly we get that the joint distribution of $(\int_0^t W - \int_0^s W)$ $1 \leq W \leq k$ is a k dimensional normal distribution. As the components of a k dimensional normally distributed vector are independent if and only if they are uncorrelated.

It follows that $(\int_0^t W) - (\int_0^s W)$ $(W = 1, 2, \dots, k)$ are independent. The almost sure continuity of (t) as a function of t can be proved as follows:-

If $2^s \leq n < 2^{s+1}$.

$W_n(x) = \prod_{k=1}^s R_k(x)$ where $W_{n-2^s}(x)$ is a product of the

Rademacher functions $R_k(x), k \leq s$ and thus is constant on every interval of the form $(\frac{r}{2^s}, \frac{r+1}{2^s})$

On the other hand the indefinite integral of $R_{s+1}(x)$ over $(\frac{r}{2^s}, \frac{r+1}{2^s})$ increase linearly from increases linearly from zero to $\frac{1}{2^{s+1}}$ and the decrease linearly to zero.

It follows that

$$\sum_{n=2^s}^{2^{s+1}-1} \xi_n \int_0^t W_n(x) dx$$

is for fixed $\omega \in \Omega$ a continuous function of t such that on every interval $(\frac{r}{2^s}, \frac{r+1}{2^s})$ varies between

$$\pm \sum_{n=2^s}^{2^{s+1}-1} \xi_n \epsilon_{nr}$$

Now the sum $\sum_{n=2^s}^{2^{s+1}-1} \xi_n \epsilon_{nr}$ is normally distributed with variance 2^s

Thus put $\delta_{st} = \sum_{n=2^s}^{2^{s+1}-1} \xi_n \epsilon_{nr}$

$$P[\delta_{st} > s^{2s/2}] < e^{-s^2/2}$$

Borel cantelli lemma $\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} e^{-s^2/2}$ is convergent for almost all $\omega \in \Omega$

$$\max_{1 \leq r < 2^s} |\delta_{st}| < s^{2s/2} \text{ for all but a finite number of values of } s.$$

This implies that for almost all values of ω , one has uniformly for $0 \leq t < 1$

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \left| \sum_{n=2^s}^{2^{s+1}-1} \xi_n(\omega) \int_0^t W_n(x) dx \right| < \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{2^s}{2^s} = \dots$$

Therefore $\eta_s(t)$ is for almost all ω the sum of a uniformly convergent series of continuous function. (i.e.,) it is almost surely a continuous function of t .

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

I have no conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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